

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR STUDY OF BASALT FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER BARS IN FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses the behavior of reinforced concrete beams with polymeric bars reinforced with basalt fibers (BFRP) and the addition of dispersed synthetic fibers into the mixture. Two beams with BFRP rebars were subjected to bending tests. Steel stirrups were used to avoid shear failure. It is observed that the addition of fibers contributed with a small increase in the load capacity and influenced the crack opening restriction. Analytical verifications were performed according to ACI 440.1R-15 and the Recommended Practice of IBRACON/ABECE. Both underestimated the deflection values of the beams. The prediction of crack opening by the Recommended Practice presents values higher than the experimental results.

KEYWORDS

BFRP bars; reinforced concrete beam; synthetic fibers.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete structures with steel rebars can have their long-term performance deteriorated in aggressive environments due to rebar corrosion (Huang et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021). An alternative is the use of FRP rebars (Fiber Reinforced Polymer). Glass, carbon, and aramid are conventional fibers that already have wide applicability in civil construction. Recently, a new composite material, Basalt Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (BFRP), was developed in rebar form for concrete structures (El Refai et al., 2015). This material presents non-magnetic properties, corrosion resistance, impermeability to chloride ions and chemical attacks, high tensile strength and low weight (ACI 440.1R, 2015). However, they exhibit low Young's Modulus, linear elastic behavior and brittle failure. Thus, reinforced concrete structures with GFRP e BFRP rebars have excessive deflections and larger crack width than conventional steel structures.

Some attempts at increasing the performance of concrete structures with FRP rebars include improving the compressive properties of concrete so that the high tensile strengths of the bars can be better exploited (Abed & Alhafiz, 2019).

Another practice is the addition of fibers to FRP-reinforced concrete, as it presents a more uniform distribution of cracks, in addition to reducing the width of the crack, improving the toughness and ductility of the concrete. (Attia et al., 2019).

Zhu et al. (2018) analyzed the flexure behavior of high-strength concrete beams partially reinforced with dispersed fibers. The lower (tensile) layer of the beam was casted with fiber reinforced concrete while the upper (compressive) layer was cast with plain concrete. Eleven BFRP-reinforced concrete beams were tested varying the height of the lower concrete layer, the volume ratio of fibers and the rebars ratio. A reference beam with steel rebars was also cast. The results showed that the fiber addition increased the load capacity significantly, reduced the deflection (23.5% to 52.33% lower than the reference) and crack width by 22.74% to 55.97%. The addition of fibers in the tensile zone proved to

be an effective and economical solution to overcome the large deflections and crack width of reinforced concrete beams with BFRP rebars.

Abed & Alhafiz (2019) investigated the effect of adding basalt microfiber and synthetic macrofiber to concrete on the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams with BFRP rebars. They observed that the addition of basalt and synthetic fibers to concrete increased the maximum load capacity of the concrete beams and improved the ductility curvature. The increase was higher for concrete beams with synthetic fibers.

This work deals with the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams with basalt fiber reinforced polymer (BFRP) rebars, with the addition of synthetic dispersed fibers to the mixture in order to improve the post-cracking behavior of the structural element and its overall performance. The BFRP rebars were tested in order to determine their mechanical properties. Then concrete beams were designed and cast. They were tested under four-point bending tests and the results analysed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Material properties

Reinforcing bars

In this study, basalt fiber reinforced polymer (BFRP) bars with 10 mm in diameter were used as rebars in concrete beams. Samples from these bars were tested to determine their mechanical properties including the ultimate tensile strength, Young's Modulus and bond strength, as reported in Table 1. The tensile strength and Young's Modulus tests follow the specifications of (ASTM D7205/D7205M, 2021) and the pullout test to determine the adhesion of the bar to the concrete follows the recommendations of (ASTM D7913/D7913M, 2020).

Table 1: Mechanical properties of BFRP bar.

Bar	Bar diameter (mm)	Cross sectional area (mm ²)	Tensile stress (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Bond strength (MPa)
BFRP	10.1	80.12	1012.92	52.59	20.77

Fiber

Dispersed synthetic fibers were used as concrete reinforcement. The fiber have a length of 54 mm, a density of 0.91 g/cm³ and a tensile strength of 550 MPa, according to the manufacturer's specifications.

Concrete

Synthetic fibers were added at 1.0% of the total concrete volume. The design of the concrete mix is shown in Table 2. The mechanical properties of the concrete at 28 days including compressive strength, tensile strength and Young's Modulus are summarized in Table 3. The tensile strength $f_{ct,m}$ was determined according to NBR 12142 (2010). In addition, the tensile residual strength was assessed according to NBR 16940 (2021). These results are shown in Figure 1. Concrete with addition of fibers received the nomenclature (F) and concrete without addition of fibers (plain concrete) is denominated as (NF).

Table 2: Concrete mix design.

Specimen	Cement (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	Gravel (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Superplasticizer (kg/m ³)	Fiber content (kg/m ³)
NF	400.83	809.68	1002.10	200.42	0.4	-
F	396.80	801.60	992.00	198.40	0.8	9,1

Table 3: Mechanical properties of concrete mixes.

Specimen	f_{cm} (MPa)	Standard Test	COV (%)	$f_{ct,m}$ (MPa)	Standard Test	COV (%)	$E_{ci,m}$ (GPa)	Standard Test	COV (%)
NF	47.39	NBR 5739, (2018)	19.23	5.37	NBR 12142, (2010)	11.05	34.42	NBR 8522, (2017)	6.19
F	40.34		15.50	5.68		10.50	29.67		14.19

f_{cm} – average compressive strength; $f_{ct,m}$ – average tensile strength; $E_{ci,m}$ – average Young's Modulus

Figure 1 shows the result of the tensile stress versus CMOD diagram for the tensile and flexural test on concrete prisms with the addition of dispersed fibers. The experiments consist of three-point bending tests over a span of 500 mm. Prismatic specimens of 550 mm long, 150 mm width and 150 mm height were used. A 25 mm notch was cut using a circular saw in the concrete layer in the middle of the span to localize the crack initiation. The supports are located 25 mm from the beam's ends.

The beam is loaded at its mid-span. Displacement is applied and the force P is read. A clip gauge was positioned in the notch to register the crack mouth aperture (CMOD), which controlled the tests. An initial displacement rate of 0.05 mm/min was established and once the crack aperture reached 0.1 mm, the displacement rate was increased to 0.20 mm/min.

Figure 1: Tensile stress-CMOD diagram for tensile flexural testing of fibrous concrete.

Concrete beams

This study included two rectangular concrete beams reinforced with BFRP rebars. The beams specimens were 2000 mm long with rectangular cross-section of 150 x 300 mm, with clear span of 1900 mm. Beams were reinforced longitudinally with four BFRP rebars (10 mm diameter) arranged in two layers. Two steel bar of 6,3 mm were used as top reinforcement and steel stirrup of 6,3 mm diameter spaced at 130 mm were used as shear reinforcement in the beams. Steel stirrups were used to avoid shear failure. Figure 2 shows the beam arrangement. Figure 3 shows the cross-section of the tested beams.

Figure 2: Dimensions and reinforcement details of beams without confinement (unit cm).

Figure 3: Beam specimen cross-section (unit cm).

The specimens were designed to fail by concrete crushing in the constant moment zone, in accordance with ACI 440.1R (2015) and Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021). This was accomplished by using a reinforcement ratio (ρ_f) greater than the balanced reinforced ratio (ρ_{fb}). The ratio between the reinforcement and balanced reinforcement was 2.44 according to ACI 440.1R (2015) and 2.04 according to Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021).

Instrumentation

Figure 4 provides instrumentation details. All test were conducted using a portico with a 600 kN load capacity. The beams were tested using four-point bending tests with the load divided equally over a constant moment region of 380 mm. One LVDT 1-WA/50mm-T was used to measure the deflection at half of the beam span. The strains of the longitudinal BFRP rebars were measured with two electrical-resistance strain gauges (E1), as shown in Figure 2.

Crack widths were obtained using Digital Image Correlation (DIC). This technique consists of recording and tracking images of the surface of interest with a set of randomly spaced points. For this, the beams surface (380 x 300 mm) was painted white with randomly spaced black dots. In addition, the image capture was done by a cell phone camera, using Lens Buddy application. To avoid illumination variation on the surface, a light source composed of LED lamps was used.

Figure 4: Test setup.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Flexural capacity and mode of failure

The load-deflection curves of the tested beam specimens are shown in Figure 5. The addition of fibers did not promote any significant difference in the load x displacement behavior. The failure mode of the tested beams can be seen in Figure 6. The cracking pattern changed, with smaller and less thick cracks in the fiber reinforced beam (B-F).

Figure 5: Load – Midspan deflection graph of the tested beams.

Figure 6: Failure mode of the BFRP-reinforced beams. a) Plain concrete; b) Fiber reinforced concrete.

Table 4 provides the maximum measured values for loads, mid-span deflection, failure mode, and the bending capacity (M_{exp}). The beam B-F resulted in an ultimate load of 135.88 kN at 32.81 mm of mid-span deflection and B-NF resulted in an ultimate load of 148.66 kN with a deflection of 49.00 mm. Compared to B-NF, the increase in flexion ability was 9.41%.

The ultimate capacity of the beam was compared to the prediction value using the ACI 440.1R (2015) approach and the Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021). These results compared with the experimental values in Table 4. The comparisons indicate good agreement between the theoretical and experimental values.

Table 4: Load, deflection, failure mode and ultimate moment.

Beam	Ultimate load (kN)	Deflection at ultimate load (mm)	Failure mode	M_{exp} (kNm)	ACI 440.1R	Recom. Practice
					M_{exp}/M_n	M_{exp}/M_n
B-NF	135.88	32.81	CC	51.63	1.04	0.92
B-F	148.66	49.00	CC	56.49	1.13	1.00

CC – concrete crushing;

Tensile strength in BFRP rebars

Figure 7 shows the tensile strain in the BFRP rebar versus the applied load. It presents a typical curve: an initial behavior when concrete is in a pre-cracking state. In post-cracking state the strain varies linearly with the increasing load until failure. For the beam B-NF (without addition of fibers), the rebar presented greater deformation for the same load than the B-F beam. This difference is attributed to the tensile strength of the fibers that withstand part of the tensile stresses.

Figure 7: Load – strain in longitudinal rebar.

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was performed using the GOM Correlate software to obtain vertical displacement and crack width. Figure 8 compares the applied load versus the vertical displacement measured with the LVDT and obtained using DIC. The plots are in very good agreement.

Figure 8: Load - vertical displacement at midspan: (Left) B-F beam; (Right) B-NF beam. Legend (E) indicates the LVDT measurements and (G) indicates the Digital Images Correlation values.

The DIC process was applied to determine the crack width at the center of the beam. Table 5 provides the crack widths at service and ultimate load. Figure 9 shows the curves load – crack width of the tested beams. It is clear that the addition of disperse fibers promoted a significant reduction in crack width. Considering the crack width limit of 0.7 mm established by design codes, both tested beams showed excessive values of crack width at service load.

Table 5: Crack width at service load and ultimate.

Beam	Crack width (at service load) (mm)	Ultimate crack width (mm)
B-SF	1.45	5.01
B-F	0.98	3.25

Figure 9: Load - crack width of the tested beams.

THEORETICAL STUDY ON SERVICE LOAD/COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EXPERIMENTAL AND PREDICTED RESULTS

Deflection response/mid-span deflection

Deflection predictions were determined according to ACI 440.1R (2015) and Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021). Figure 10 compares the experimental and predicted deflections. Table 6 provides the experimental deflection measured at load service (40% of the ultimate load) and the experimental-to-predicted deflection ratios. Both ACI 440.1R (2015) and Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021) underestimate the deflection value for reinforced concrete beams with BFRP rebars at service load.

Considering deflection limits at service load, $L/240$ for ACI 440.1R (2015) and $L/250$ for the Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021) we obtain 7.92 mm and 7.6 mm, respectively. The beams exhibited deflections greater than the limit established by ACI 440.1R (2015) and the Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021) at service load.

Figure 10: Comparison between the experimental and predicted deflection

Table 6: Experimental deflection at service load and experimental-to-predicted deflection.

Beam	ACI 440.1R (2015)		Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021)	
	Deflection at 52 kN (mm)	$\frac{Deflection_{EXP}}{Deflection_{ACI}}$	Deflection at 59 kN (mm)	$\frac{Deflection_{EXP}}{Deflection_{Rec.P.}}$
B-SF	10.24	1.78	12.02	3.24
B-F	10.27	1.79	12.24	3.30

The crack width prediction was calculated according to Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021). Figure 11 compares the experimental curve of beams B-NF and B-F and the predicted load-crack width for plain concrete and fiber reinforced concrete.

Table 7 provides a comparison between experimental crack width measured at service load and experimental-predicted crack width ratio. The theoretical proposition underestimates the crack width values with smaller crack widths at the same load compared to the experimental observations (B-NF and B-F).

Table 7: Experimental crack width at service load and experimental-to-predicted crack width.

Beam	Crack width at service load (mm)	$\frac{Crack\ width_{EXP}}{Crack\ width_{Rec.P.}}$
B-SF	1.45	1.56
B-F	0.92	1.67

Figure 11: Comparison between the experimental and predicted crack width (plain concrete and fiber reinforced concrete).

CONCLUSIONS

This work addresses the behavior of reinforced concrete beams with polymeric bars reinforced with basalt fibers (BFRP) and the addition of dispersed synthetic fibers into the mixture. Steel stirrups were used to avoid shear failure. The results allow some conclusions, as follows:

- The fiber addition in the beam B-F contributed with the increase of load capacity, failing by concrete crushing.
- The reinforced concrete beams with BFRP rebars showed bilinear behavior for deflection and reinforcement strain. The pre-cracking response of beams were almost not influenced by fiber addition since this phase is governed by concrete tension strength. The BFRP rebar in beam B-NF presented large deformation.
- The theoretical analysis, according to ACI 440.1R (2015) and Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021), underestimated the deflection value of reinforced concrete beams with BFRP bars.
- In crack width prediction for beam based on Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021) lower values of crack width were found for the same load compared to the experimental result of the tested beams (B-SF and B-F).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.